

EFFECTIVENESS AND PERFORMANCES OF BIOGAS PRODUCED FROM COW DUNG AND CATTLE RUMEN

Inetianbor, O.C¹, *Isola, O. B.², Ekozin, A. A.², Isah, A.¹

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¹Department of Chemistry, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria

²Chemical Sciences Department, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: ibamiji@sau.edu.ng; Tel: +2348156390725

ABSTRACT

Renewable energy is steadily gaining importance and leading the way towards sustainability as the need to achieve secure and environmentally friendly energy sources arises not only to satisfy the increasing world population but to forestall present and future energy problems. Anaerobic digestion of organic waste from animals creates low-molecular-weight compounds such as methane, CO₂, ammonia, and organic acid. In this research, samples of cow dung (CD) and cattle rumen (CR) were collected from an abattoir in Benin City, Nigeria and digested in a conventional single-phase digester reactor with a retention time of 14 days. The physicochemical properties of the substrates for CR and CD were pH (4.9), total solids (76, 81.8) %, moisture content (31, 27) %, volatile matter (23.4, 32.5) %, ash content (5.6, 9.3) %, nitrogen (0.42, 0.76) %, hydrogen (2.115, 2.449) %, and oxygen (21.634, 18.6501) %. The results also showed that 5076 cm³ and 3548 cm³ of biogas were produced optimally on the fourteenth day with a pH of 7 and an ambient temperature of 30°C to 34°C for CR and CD fermentation respectively. The production of biogas from CR had a longer digestion and fermentation period than CD. A higher percentage of the gaseous fuel, CH₄(g), was obtained in the CD (68.78%) than in the CR (52.21%) samples. However, the cumulative gas collection study showed that CR content had a better overall performance than the CD.

Keywords: renewable energy, biogas, cow dung, cattle rumen, anaerobic digestion

INTRODUCTION

The problem of climate change, environmental degradation, and various health issues we experience today is a consequence of overdependence on fossil fuels as the primary energy source. Enormous amounts of garbage or waste produced industrially and through agricultural activities could lead to unsanitary environmental conditions that promote the growth of hazardous microbes if not properly managed. Besides the health risks, improper waste management pollutes the environment and makes it unappealing. However, converting waste into biogas can produce a valuable and environmentally friendly form of energy (Ozor et al., 2014).

Livestock waste management is a global problem that requires urgent attention to ensure that waste can be effectively and efficiently managed without causing environmental issues. With the increase in feedlot farming, large quantities of cow dung are being produced. A significant portion of this waste is either disposed of in landfills or applied to

land without treatment. In Nigeria, animal waste production is estimated to exceed 227,500 tonnes of fresh waste per day. Interestingly, 1 kg of animal excrement can produce 0.03 m³ of gas per day, meaning Nigeria could theoretically produce 6.8 million m³ of biogas daily, equivalent to about 3.9 million litres of petroleum energy (Abubakar and Ismai, 2012). Additionally, many people in developing and underdeveloped countries rely on wood or charcoal for energy, primarily in rural areas, leading to deforestation. With fossil-based fuels becoming more limited and expensive, alternative and sustainable energy sources are essential.

Renewable energy sources like biogas are produced from organic wastes, animal manure, sewage sludge, and more (Gondra, 2010). Other sources include biodegradable garbage, straw, by-products from agriculture and industry, and sugarcane, as well as specially produced energy crops (Raja and Wazir, 2017). The anaerobic digestion of organic waste from biomass, humans, and animals through fermentation

generates energy by converting organic matter into usable gases (Adeniran et al., 2014). Anaerobic digestion is an efficient method for converting waste to energy, as biomass polymers are broken down into smaller molecules with the aid of microorganisms. This process produces methane, carbon dioxide, and traces of other gases (Raja and Wazir, 2017). An estimated 13.3 million tonnes of CH₄ emissions can be prevented annually with the anaerobic treatment of animal manure and energy utilization of the methane produced (Andritz, 2015).

Cattle dung, which is the residue of undigested food material excreted by herbivorous bovine animals, is a mixture of feces and urine in a 3:1 ratio and contains lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose. It has been found to contain 24 different minerals, including nitrogen, sulfur, potassium, and trace amounts of iron, magnesium, copper, cobalt, manganese, and more. Animal wastes are excellent materials for methane generation. In countries with less established biogas technologies, cattle and buffalo dung are commonly used as feed for digesters. Mixing the excrement with water (slurry) creates a homogeneous mixture, easing the digestive process. Poultry dung, goat, sheep, horse, and elephant manure are also excellent sources of biogas.

The problem of inadequate energy can be addressed by converting seemingly low-cost waste into energy, improving living conditions in many countries. Inability to manage waste disposal and secure sufficient energy has a significant impact on living conditions. Fuel scarcity and waste disposal are major issues in Nigeria and other developing countries. Waste-generated energy is necessary, as it will clean the environment while also providing a more affordable energy source. This research was carried out to determine the effectiveness of producing biogas from cow dung and cow rumen by analyzing the physicochemical properties of the feedstocks and the biogas produced.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

- a. **Sample:** Cow dung and cattle rumen content.
- b. **Reagents:**
 - i. Distilled water, used in preparing the feedstock and for washing apparatus.
 - ii. Soap, for washing the apparatus/equipment.

c. Apparatus/equipment:

- Bio-Gas Analyzer (Henan Bosean Bh-4A) Portable Multi-Gas Detector and Analyzer
- Mercury-in-glass thermometer (Jinotech)
- pH Meter (Unican model C)
- Stirrer (Jinotech)
- Analytical weighing balance (OHAUS Pioneer)
- Gas pipe or Hose
- Bio-digester (Locally fabricated PVC tank)
- Beakers (Pyrex - 50ml, 250ml, 500ml, and 1000ml)
- Measuring Cylinder

Sample Collection

Cow dung and cattle rumen content were collected fresh from an abattoir in Benin City.

Slurry Preparation

The freshly collected feedstock was mixed with an adequate quantity of water in a 1:2 ratio and stirred thoroughly with a wooden stirrer, then transferred into the bio-digester for maximum biogas production as described by Adeniran et al. (2014).

Design of Bio-Digester

The bio-digester vessel was constructed using a 25-liter plastic tank with dimensions of 50 cm by 30 cm. The tank was drilled with a hot iron: one hole at the top for a 0.9 cm diameter rubber hose and another near the base for a 2 cm diameter hose to serve as an inlet for the substrates. The 0.9 cm hose, 70 cm in length, connected to a 500 ml cylinder for gas volume collection. The 2 cm hose at the base connected a valve for discharge and recharging of the substrate. All perforations were sealed with rubber tubes and adhesive to ensure the system was airtight (Shobhit et al., 2016).

Bio-digester Set-up and Loading

Each bio-digester was loaded with 2 kg of substrate in a batch, and a wooden stirrer was used to continuously stir the slurry, ensuring proper mixing for enhanced gas production. The experiment was conducted under ambient conditions with no control over temperature, pressure, or pH. Adequate space was left at the top of the digester for biogas storage.

Biogas Collection and Storage

The gas produced flowed through a rubber hose into a nylon tube connected to the top of the bio-digester. The volume of biogas yield was measured as the equivalent of water displaced from a 1000 ml cylinder. The cylinder was refilled after complete displacement. An acidified brine solution was used to prevent the dissociation of biogas in the water, prepared by adding NaCl to water until a supersaturated solution was formed. Six to eight drops of sulfuric acid were added to acidify the brine solution. Since biogas is insoluble in brine, pressure builds up to displace the solution (Ukpai and Nnabuchi, 2012; Adeniran et al., 2014).

Compositional Analysis of Biogas

The presence of combustible gas was tested by lighting a flame on a Bunsen burner connected to the digester's gas discharge pipe. The gas's combustibility, flame color, and odor were determined following the methods described by Ozor et al. (2014). The biogas composition was analyzed using a Henan Bosean Bh-4A Portable Multi-Gas Detector and Analyzer. The gas exit pipe was connected to a gas sampler, which was then attached to the analyzer's gas sensor. The composition was displayed as percentages and in parts per million (ppm) on the screen.

Physico-chemical Analysis of Animal Feedstock

Ash Content

Exactly 1.0 g of pulverized samples were weighed into platinum crucibles and subjected to a temperature of 850°C in a muffle furnace for 4 hours until a constant weight was attained (AOAC, 1995).

Moisture Content

Moisture content was determined by weighing 1.0 g of powdered samples in an evaporating dish, then heating at 110°C for 1 hour in an air-dry oven until a constant weight was achieved (AOAC, 1995).

Volatile Matter

Volatile matter was determined by heating 1 g of sample in a 10 ml platinum crucible at 225°C for 60 minutes in an air-dry oven. The weight loss was measured before and after heating.

Fixed Carbon

Fixed carbon (FC) was estimated according to the following formula:

$$FC = 100\% - (M + V + A)$$

where M is the moisture content, V is the volatile matter, and A is the ash content.

Hydrogen and Oxygen Content

Total hydrogen and oxygen contents were estimated based on the atomic weights of H₂O, as described by ISO 1170.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Substrate Characterization

Table 1 shows the physicochemical properties of the substrates used in biogas production before microbial digestion (fermentation). These properties help estimate the level of fermentation achievable during the digestion process.

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Table 1: Physicochemical properties of the substrates

Property	Cattle Rumen Content	Cow Dung
pH	4.9	4.9
Total Solid (%)	76.0	81.8
Moisture Content (%)	31	27
Volatile Matter (%)	23.4	32.5
Ash Content (%)	5.6	9.3
Nitrogen (%)	0.42	0.76
Hydrogen Content (%)	2.115	2.499
Oxygen Content (%)	21.634	18.6501

Total solids were observed to be high in the samples, 76% and 81.8% for cattle rumen content and cow dung, respectively. The samples were acidic, with pH values of 4.9 for both.

Biogas Yield

The amount of volatile solid content in the biomass is an important parameter for evaluating the biogas production process. Biogas production was measured daily over a period of 14 days. The biogas generation was instantaneous due to the rapid fermentation of the animal waste (Figure 1). Polysaccharides are easily degraded by microbes through enzymatic hydrolysis.

Daily biogas generation from cow dung and cattle rumen content did not follow the same pattern.

Figure 1: Daily biogas production from cow dung and cattle rumen content

Figure 1 shows that biogas production was rapid in cow dung compared to cattle rumen content during the first 4 days due to the high level of bioactivity and fermentation of the highly degraded substrate in the cow dung. Cattle rumen content showed a slower initial biogas generation but increased its gaseous output starting on the 5th day, likely due to an amplified rate of fermentation of the digestible substrate.

Besides the quantity of digestible matter in the substrates, the continuous and timely evacuation of the gaseous products (biogas) may also influence the biogas generation rate. The tests revealed that the more gas was removed from the system, the more it was replaced. The cumulative gas collection study showed that cattle rumen content had better overall performance (Figure 2).

Biogas Compositional Analysis

The compositional analysis of the biogas was conducted using a Henan Bosean Bh-4A Portable Multi-Gas Detector and Analyzer. Table 2 displays the results. It can be observed that the generated biogas contains carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and

hydrogen sulfide (H₂S). Cattle rumen produced a slightly higher amount of H₂S (0.12%) compared to cow dung (0.11%). This could be due to the presence of higher lignin and hemicellulose content in the cattle rumen substrate, which is degraded by a specific microbial community.

Table 2: Compositional analysis of gas generation from cow dung and cattle rumen content

Component	Cattle Rumen Content	Cow Dung
CH ₄ (%)	52.21	68.78
CO ₂ (%)	47.67	31.11
H ₂ S (%)	0.12	0.11

Table 2 shows that a higher percentage of methane (CH₄) was generated from cow dung than from cattle rumen content. Cow dung also produced lower levels of noxious gases (CO₂ and H₂S) compared to cattle rumen content.

Figure 2: Cumulative biogas recovery from cow dung and cattle rumen content

Qualitative Test for Methane in Biogas Produced

The presence of methane was tested by lighting a flame on a Bunsen burner connected to the digester. The gas emitted from the digester was checked to see whether it burns, and both the flame color and odor were observed, following the method described by Ozor et al. (2014).

CONCLUSION

The feedstock used in this study influenced not only the generation of biogas at ambient conditions but also the composition, generation, and quality of the biogas produced. Biogas generated from cow dung was found to be richer in $\text{CH}_4(\text{g})$ than that from cattle rumen, though both had low $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$ concentrations due to their low cellulose content, which would otherwise have been fermented to release more $\text{CO}_2(\text{g})$.

The quality of the biogas improved with increasing CH_4 content, while the CO_2 and H_2S contents decreased slightly. Compared to conventional fuels, biogas is a sustainable energy source that does not contribute to environmental pollution. Its production helps reduce the large amounts of animal dung and waste in the environment, thus preventing nitrogen pollution and eutrophication. Furthermore,

biogas production mitigates methane emissions from uncontrolled landfills.

Biogas production can be upgraded to replace natural gas for transportation, domestic, and industrial fuel needs, as well as for electricity generation, providing an eco-friendly alternative to fossil fuels.

References

- Abubakar, B. S. U. I., Ismail, N. (2012). Anaerobic digestion of cow dung for biogas production. *ARPJN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 7(2), 169-172.
- Adeniran, A. K., Ahaneku, I. E., Itodo, I. N., Rohjy, H. A. (2014). Relative effectiveness of biogas production using poultry wastes and cow dung. *Agric Eng Int: CIGR Journal*, 16(1), 126-132.
- Andritz, W. (2015). *Biogas – An important renewable energy source*. World Bioenergy Association, Holländargatan. Retrieved from <http://www.worldbioenergy.org> on December 31, 2021.
- AOAC International. (1995). *Official methods of analysis of AOAC International* (17th ed.). Association of Analytical Communities, Gaithersburg, MD, USA.

Gondra, Z. A. (2010). Study of factors influencing the quality and yield of biodiesel produced by transesterification of vegetable oils. *Digitala Vetenskapliga Arkivet*. Retrieved from <https://urn:nbn:se:hig:diva-6934>

Ozor, O. C., Agah, M. V., Ogbu, K. I., Nnachi, A. U., Agwu, M. M. (2014). Biogas production using cow dung from Abakaliki abattoir in South-Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Technology Research*, 3(10), 237-239.

Raja, I. A., Wazir, S. (2017). Biogas production: The fundamental processes. *Universal Journal of Engineering Science*, 5(2), 29-37.

Shobhit, S., Sunil, K., Kapil, S. (2016). Bottling of biogas – A renewable approach. *The Engineering Journal of Application Scopes*, 1(2), 28-32.

Ukpai, P. A., Nnabuchi, M. N. (2012). Comparative study of biogas production from cow dung, cow pea and cassava peeling using 45 litres biogas digester. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 3(3), 1864-1869.